

INGLIZ TILINI POTENSIAL LUG'AT VA MASHQLAR
YORDAMIDA O'RGANISH MASALASI

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2 son politexnikumi ingliz tili fani o'qituvchilari**

Annotasiya: Maqolada ingliz tilini lug'at va mashqlar yordamida o'rgatish masalasida leksik bilimlarga, ko'nikmalarga tayanib, reseptiv nutq faoliyatida uchraydigan leksikaning katta qatlamini tushunish, yangi so'z ma'nosini mustaqil fahmlash bo'yicha ko'nikmalar hosil qilish masalasi haqida qisqacha fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Ingliz tili, birikma, so'z, leksika, bilim.

Аннотация: В статье рассматривается вопрос обучения английскому языку с помощью словарей и упражнений с опорой на лексические знания и умения, понимание большого пласта лексики, встречающейся в рецептивной речевой деятельности, формирование навыков самостоятельного понимания значения новых слов. кратко обсуждается.

Ключевые слова: английский язык, сочетание, слово, лексика, знание.

Abstract: The article discusses the issue of teaching English with the help of dictionaries and exercises based on lexical knowledge and skills, understanding a large layer of vocabulary found in receptive speech activity, and developing skills for independently understanding the meaning of new words. discussed briefly.

Key words: English language, combination, word, vocabulary, knowledge.

Ingliz tilini o'qitishda muhim jihatlardan biri bo'lgan potensial lug'at boyligi haqida o'rganish bugungi dolzarb masalalardan biridir. Bu lug'atni o'zlashtirish

to'g'risida emas, balki uni shakllantirish va kengaytirish, naqd (real) leksik bilimlarga, aniqrog'i, ko'nikmalarga tayanib, reseptiv nutq faoliyatida uchraydigan leksikaning katta qatlamini tushunish, yangi so'z ma'nosini mustaqil fahmlash bo'yicha ko'nikmalar hosil qilish borasida gap yuritiladi.

So'z yasash, konversiya, baynalmilal leksika, so'z birikmalari, ko'p ma'nolilik kabilar potensial lug'at manbai bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Til tajribasi tufayli o'quvchi ushbu leksik birliklarni tanib olish imkoniyati bor bo'lgani uchun mustaqil idrok etib tushunish ko'nikmasini egallaydi. Mustaqil o'rganishda yana bir foydali pedagogik usul – lug'at va ma'lumotnomalardan yangi leksik birlik ma'nosini topishdir.

Leksika ko'nikmalarini shakllantirishda mashq qilish bosqichidagi asosiy ishlar quyidagilar:

1. So'z, so'z birikmasi va gapni aytish. O'qituvchi yoki diktor nutqiga taqlidiy aytish. Ushbu usul amali chog'ida o'qituvchi topshirig'i mana bunday tartibda bo'lishi kuzatiladi: “Mendan keyin takrorlang va eslab qoling (Repeat and remember)”. Diktor nutqini tinglash paytida esa “Eshiting, orasida takrorlang va eslab qoling (Listen, repeat and remember)” qabilida o'quvchilar topshiriq oladilar. Mazkur mashq xor bilan va yakka tartibda o'tkaziladi. Esda saqlab qolishga, albatta, ko'rsatma berilishi shart. Diktor nutqiga ergashib, xor bilan qaytarish samara berishi muqarrar, biroq yolg'iz takror aytilishi ham (boshqalar ichida aytadi) ijobiy natijalar garovidir.

2. Yangi so'z ishtirokida so'z birikmalarini og'zaki tuzish. O'qituvchi quyidagicha topshiriq beradi: So'zlarni eshiting va ularni so'z birikmasida ayting. Masalan, birinchi o'quv yilida o'rganilayotgan book so'zi mashq qilinyapti. O'qituvchi so'zlar guruhini aytadi: English, Uzbek, Russian, read, see, my. O'quvchilar navbatma-navbat birikmalar tuzadilar: English book, read a book, my book, Uzbek book... So'z birikmalari yasash ko'nikmasi nutq yuritishni o'rganishning muhim tarkibiy qismi bo'lganligidan, o'qituvchi rahbarligida bunday mashq qilish juda foydalidir.

3. So'zni turli nutq namunalarda qo'llash. O'qituvchi topshirig'iga binoan bajariladigan ish turidir. Masalan. "Aytin I see a...". "Savolga javob qaytaring...", "O'rtog'ingizdan so'rang", "Aytilgan fikrni quvatlang yoki inkor eting" kabilar. Nutq oqimida so'zni turli birikmalarda ishlatishni mashq qilishga erishiladi. Topshiriqlar guruh bo'lib, juft bo'lib, yolg'iz bajarilishi mumkin.

4. So'zni ko'rish orqali idrok etish, matn ma'nosiga bog'lab biriktirish va o'qish. O'qituvchi-diktor ortidan yoki mustaqil mashq qildirish mumkin. Topshiriq turlari: "Menga quloq solib, o'qing...", "Diktorni eshiting va undan keyin o'qing...", Avval ichingizda, so'ng ovoz chiqarib o'qing" kabilar. So'zning tovush timsoli o'rganilgach, uning yozuvdagi shakli o'zlashtiriladi.

5. Leksik birlikni bosma matnga tayanib, mashqda o'zlashtirish. "Berilgan matndan muayyan mavzuga oid so'zlarni toping va ularni o'qing" singari topshiriq turlari bajariladi.

6. So'zni yozish. Topshiriq: "So'zni doskadan-kitobdan ko'chiring va eslab qoling". O'qituvchi tushuntirib beradi va yozishdan yagona muddao ushbu so'zni eslab qolish ekanligini uqtiradi.

7. Yozma vazifalarni sinfda va uyda bajarish. Topshiriq namunalari: "Tushirib qoldirilgan so'zni topib yozing", "Berilgan harflardan so'z tuzing", "qavs ichidagi so'zlarning tegishlisini qo'yib, gaplarni ko'chiring" va h.k.z. Mashq qilish chog'ida o'quvchilarga oqilona usullardan foydalanish yo'llarini o'rgatish kerak, toki ular oz kuch va vaqt sarflab, samarali natijalami qo'lga kiritsinlar. Mashq qilish bosqichida qo'lanadigan ushbu usul va topshiriqlar ta'limning dastlabki yillariga ko'proq mos keladi. Boshqa bosqichlarda ham ulardan foydalansa bo'ladi. Leksik operasiyalarning nutqda erkin qo'llanishi darajasiga erishmoq uchun taqdimot va mashq qilish bosqichlari bilan chegaralanish kifoya qilmaydi. Tadqiqotchi A.N.Leontev ta'biricha, "mustahkamlangan operasiyalar" ko'nikma, deb qaraladi. So'zni lug'at birligi, o'quv birligi, leksik birlik yoki ma'no birligi hisoblashdan tashqari, zamonaviy metodikada unga funksional jihatdan qo'llanish birligi, ya'ni nutqiy faoliyat birligi, deb qarash odat tusiga kirgan. Demak,

leksikaning taqdimoti, uni mashq qilish bilan chegaralanmasdan, albatta, funksional – qo'llanish vazifasini o'tashiga erishmoq zarur.

Xullasa o'rnida aytish mumkinki, so'zni nutqda va nutq uchun o'zlashtirish, ya'ni leksik ko'nikmani shakllantirishdan keyingi bosqich – ushbu ko'nikmani takomillashtirish nuqtasiga yetkazish, leksikani malaka bosqichida qo'llash masalasiidir.

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